

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL COMPETENCE AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF MODERN PHILOSOPHICAL EDUCATION

Usmanova Galina Nikolaevna

Lecturer at the Department of Russian Language and Literature

Faculty of Humanities and Languages

Kokand State University

Phone: 998 99 085 25 08

Abstract: This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of developing digital competencies based on pedagogical and psychological approaches. The paper discusses the pedagogical and psychological foundations for developing digital competencies using scientific approaches.

Key words: digital technologies, digital competence, digital literacy, digital society, philological education, critical thinking, creative activity, digital culture

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, "On Approval of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 Strategy and Measures for its Effective Implementation," the introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the educational and industrial sectors of our country requires improving the personnel training system based on modern requirements. To address the challenges in developing the digital competencies of future specialists, it is important to create conditions for determining their individual educational trajectory, individualize education, integrate modern pedagogical and information and communication tools into the

educational process, and organize the educational process using advanced international practices.¹

Developing digital competencies in the modern educational process plays a vital role in developing the skills of future philology teachers in working with information, critical thinking, and creative and technological activities. In the 21st century, digital technologies are rapidly developing and becoming an integral part of philological education. Developing digital competencies is essential for future philology teachers to work with information, conduct research, organize independent learning, and compete in the labor market. Developing digital competencies as an integral part of modern philological education requires future specialists to be able to work with electronic resources and use digital tools for text analysis, searching, and processing information. This requires a revision of curricula and the introduction of new disciplines related to information technology. An interdisciplinary approach combining philology, computer science, and pedagogy remains the foundation for training a new generation of specialists.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Today, it is impossible to achieve high-quality and innovative education without digital literacy. From this perspective, the issue of digital technologies is increasingly attracting the attention of scholars worldwide. In particular, the TPACK model developed by J. A. Voogt and N. Roblin (2012), Mishra and Köhler (2006), the UNESCO digital competence model (2021), as well as the works of scholars such as Ertmer (1999), Redeker (2017), and Redeker and Puni (2017) have analyzed the nature, structure, and assessment criteria of digital competencies. However,

¹2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 dated October 5, 2020 "On approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation."

many academic sources insufficiently address the practical challenges of developing digital competencies in future philologists, strategies for addressing them, and systemic approaches at the level of educational institutions.

In today's digital society, future specialists' conscious use of information, safe navigation in the media, and effective use of digital technologies are becoming key learning outcomes. Therefore, the development of digital competencies is viewed as a pedagogical and psychological challenge directly linked to the development of critical thinking, creativity, and digital culture in future teachers. Today, developing digital competencies in future philologists is a pressing issue, and a number of regulatory documents in Uzbekistan facilitate this. Specifically, measures to develop teachers' digital skills are being defined based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (2020), the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, Presidential Resolution No. PK-81 (February 28, 2022), as well as relevant orders and instructions of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The pedagogical foundations for developing digital competencies in future philology teachers are based on pedagogical principles.

One of the main principles of pedagogy is to make the student an active participant in the educational process. Digital technologies:

- create an individual learning path;
- set the pace of independent learning;
- promote the natural development of digital competence.

Among digital technologies, in addition to pedagogical ones, other digital technologies important for education can be identified:

- management (for example, ensuring automation of document management in the network of an educational organization);
- neurobiological (based on the use of sensors that allow, for example, to determine the parameters of the health and psychophysiological state of students);
- production (ensuring the formation of necessary professional knowledge)².

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Digital competence is the ability to confidently, critically reflect on, and responsibly apply digital skills in a specific context. Therefore, effective methods, digital literacy factors, pedagogical and psychological approaches, scientific findings, legal and regulatory documents were selected as the methodological basis.

The following methods are effective for developing digital competencies:

- online project and group work;
- digital laboratories;
- web quests;
- gamification (game technologies);
- blended learning methods (traditional + online learning) develop students' analytical thinking, creativity, and collaboration skills.

A future teacher's digital culture is their digital literacy, which is a key factor in developing digital competence in the classroom. The future teacher:

²Abdullaeva Barno Saifutdinovna. International Scientific and Practical Conference "Challenges and Solutions in Integrating Digital Technologies into Graphic Education," April 14, 2025, p. 23.

- has the ability to choose information resources;
- knows how to manage a virtual learning environment;
- uses online assessment systems.

It is necessary to help students create a safe digital environment.

Modernization of the educational environment and effective development of digital competencies These involve creating conditions that ensure the high-quality use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process.

The main components of such an environment are:

- technical means;
- developed Internet network;
- digital educational resources.

Developing digital competencies is essential for the professional training of modern specialists. With the rapid growth of information volumes, the skills to effectively work with data and digital resources are particularly important.

The main areas of development of digital competencies include:

- development of skills in working with information, necessary for successful educational and professional activities;
- searching for information on the Internet using modern search engines and specialized electronic resources;
- evaluation and selection of reliable sources of information, allowing to distinguish reliable data from unreliable or outdated information;
- data analysis and processing, including systematization, comparison, interpretation and critical evaluation of information;
- filtering of information flows, which helps to highlight the most significant and relevant information from a large volume of data;

- storing, organizing and presenting information in the required format using digital tools and software.

The listed skills are of particular importance in the context of information overload in modern society.

They enable future professionals to effectively navigate the digital space, make informed decisions, and successfully solve professional problems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Developing digital competencies develops information culture, media literacy, and technological skills in future specialists. Pedagogical and psychological approaches, as well as interactive teaching methods, enhance the effectiveness of digital education. The research findings serve as a methodological basis for integrating digital technologies into the educational process.

Based on the materials reviewed, we deemed it appropriate to provide a clear definition of digital competence, proposed by scholar Barno Abdullaeva: "Digital competence is a holistic human quality that develops throughout life, based on knowledge, skills, and qualifications acquired during education, and manifested in activities using digital technologies, including a system of attitudes that allows for the safe and effective selection and use of digital technologies, the ability to organize and control the process and results of activities, and their use. Digital technologies are assessed as the readiness to demonstrate one's ability to solve professional and social problems using modern information and communication technologies. Digital competence is a specific component of digital competence. Digital competence is an internal cognitive development that is subsequently realized through the use of digital technologies. Meanwhile, digital competence is personal development that is formed on the basis of digital competence.

The introduction of technology into education poses a number of challenges. One of these is the need to preserve the humanities component of education. Philology as a discipline requires in-depth text analysis, an understanding of cultural context, and the development of critical thinking. Excessive reliance on technology can lead to a superficial perception of information and a decline in analytical skills. Therefore, it is important to ensure a balance between traditional and innovative teaching methods. Furthermore, there is the problem of digital inequality, which implies unequal access to technology and educational resources. This can create additional barriers for students from different social groups. Therefore, ensuring equal access to quality education and creating conditions for the effective use of technology by all participants in the educational process is a crucial task. Indeed, to digitalize the educational process, maximize the potential didactic potential of digital technologies, and fully adapt them to solve educational problems, it is advisable to transform elements of the educational process, on the one hand, and the digital technologies and tools used in it, on the other.³

CONCLUSION

Today, the role of technology in philology and the education system is multifaceted and dynamically evolving. This contributes to the expansion of scientific opportunities, the improvement of the quality of education, and the development of new professional competencies, while innovations are becoming an integral part of the educational process, defining its content and development directions. In the context of the digital transformation of society, the ability to combine traditional humanities values with modern technological solutions is

³Abdullaeva Barno Saifutdinovna. International Scientific and Practical Conference "Challenges and Solutions in Integrating Digital Technologies into Graphic Education," April 14, 2025, p. 23.

considered particularly important, ensuring the sustainable development of philological scholarship.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Mishra P., Koehler MJ Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. – Teachers College Record, 2006.
2. Jonassen D. Computers as Mindtools for Schools. – Pearson, 2011.
3. UNESCO. ICT Competency Framework for Teachers. – Paris, 2018.
4. Becta. Digital Skills in Modern Education. – London, 2020.
5. Mavlonov A., Tursunova M. Raqamli pedagogika asoslari: O'quv qo'llanma. – Toshkent: Innovatsiya-Ziyo, 2024.
6. Abdullaeva Barno Sayfutdinovna. International scientific and practical conference “Challenges and solutions in the integration of digital technologies into the graphic education process”, APRIL 14, 2025. 23-b
7. F.Sh. Shirinov, LQ Dexqonov. Raqamli kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari. Inter education & Global Study. Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. ISSN 2992-9024 (online) 2025, vol.3.233-bet